

CULTIVATING CLIMATE CHANGE CONSCIOUSNESS: ASSESSING TEACHERS' AWARENESS AND MITIGATION PRACTICES IN ADDRESSING CLIMATE CHANGE

Sherylene S. Reyes, Bryan DC. Gabriel, PhD

*Graduate School Department, Bulacan Agricultural State College,
San Idefonso, Bulacan, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to analyze the awareness level of middle school (JHS) and high school (SHS) teachers on climate change and climate change mitigation using descriptive and purposive sampling methods. A 5-point Likert scale was used to collect data. The survey revealed that there are more female than male and more Junior High School Teachers than Senior High School Teachers that are respondents of this study. It showed that respondents are aware on the causes of climate change like greenhouse gases, fossil fuels, and activities that is related to industrial field, but they are not familiar with wind energy and dairy products as contributor to the climate change. The different ways to reduce climate change are walking, cycling, and reducing food waste, while taking the trains instead of flying was not common to the respondents. But as class type is concerned, Junior High School Teachers and Senior High School Teachers does not show a significant difference on the awareness of respondents about climate change. The findings highlight the importance of professional development programs, climate change integration on curriculum, and collaboration activities that will promote climate change education and development of climate change strategies that teachers can be used in their teaching.

Keywords: *Climate change, Awareness, Mitigation, Sequential-explanatory, Earth and life Science*

INTRODUCTION

Climate change has been a big challenge for most of the countries especially for the Philippines. Based on the World Risk Report in 2017, the Philippines place as the third most vulnerable country to climate change. It causes massive problem such as GDP annual losses, continuous changes in rainfall patterns and distribution, droughts, threats to biodiversity and food security, rise of sea level, risks in public health, and risks on vulnerable groups such as women and indigenous people (NICCDIES, 2024).

Climate change can cause the GDP loss of the Philippines up to 6% by 2100. According to the Asian Development Bank on the economics about climate change, the country's GDP can lose 6% annually if climate change will be disregarded. Aside from the GDP loss, major rainfall patterns and distributions changes can affect the country. On the report of Philippine Atmospheric Geophysical and Astronomical Services (PAGASA) last 2011, the rainfall in the country may decrease in the year 2020 except from Luzon. While in terms of heavy rainfall, the number of days is expected to be much higher with the global warming by the year 2020 and 2050 (NICCDIES, 2024).

On the Executive Brief No. 2018-01, in line with the ecosystem of the Philippines, climate change has a big impact on the grassland and coral reefs. It is estimated that 1 million hectares of grassland can be highly affected by the changes in the future. These grasslands are prone to fires especially during dryness and less rainfall during summer months. 98% of the coral reefs are nearly extinct and may die by 2050, based on the 2016 Low Carbon Monitor Report. This will continue if the global warming trends will not be ended. The fish catch may also be affected that can cause a decrease by almost 50% compared to the levels on the year 2001-2010. It just shows that climate change has a big impact on the ecosystem. Addition to this, food supply is also affected by the climate change. A decrease of 10% for each 1 degree Celsius in growing-season minimum temperature in the dry season.

Based on the Climate Change Commission (2010), the National Framework Strategy on Climate Change for the year 2010-2022 is crafted to ensure and strengthen the adaptation of the natural environment and human communities to the changes in climate. It highlighted the critical aspect of adaptation meant to be translated to all governments. The Philippine Climate Change Scenarios for year 2020 and 2050 is also projected in this framework, the annual mean temperature, annual mean rainfall, and sea level rise are discussed that shows the possible extreme events that might happen.

What are the findings that might help in understanding this climate change? As discussed on the 5th Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), there are three findings on climate change; "1.) *Human influence on the climate system is clear; 2.) anthropogenic emission of greenhouses are the highest in history; and 3.) recent climate changes have impact on human and natural system*". The Philippines is among the most top country that is affected by the climate change, that aside from the natural causes, human-work activities also contributed to climate change according to Dr. Alcala of Siliman University.

The use of fossil fuels, deforestations, and increase productivity of greenhouse gases such as burning of oil, gas, and coal are all human-made.

To lessen the contribution of the humans in climate change, there are still responses that needs action by individuals and communities such as changes in behavior, actions through the initiatives of local governments, national government agencies through national policies and programs (Alcala, n.d.).

The purpose of this study is to assess the level of awareness and mitigation practices of the Junior High School (JHS) and Senior High School teachers that helps them in relaying this knowledge to their students that might help in contributing to the solution on reducing the human-made cause of climate change.

Research Questions

This study aims to assess the level of awareness and mitigation practices of Junior High School Teachers and Senior High School Teachers on climate change.

Specifically, this sought to answer the following questions:

1. How can the profile of the respondents of the teachers be described in terms of:
 - a. Sex; and
 - b. Class type?
2. What is the level of awareness among Junior High School and Senior High School Science Teachers regarding climate change?
3. To what extent are Junior High School and Senior High School Science Teachers knowledgeable about various mitigation practices for climate change?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of awareness regarding climate change when groups are categorized by sex?
5. Is there a significant difference in knowledge on mitigation practices for climate change when groups are categorized by sex?
6. Is there a significant difference in the level of awareness regarding climate change when groups are categorized by class type?
7. Is there a significant difference in knowledge on mitigation practices for climate change when groups are categorized by class type?

METHODOLOGY

The respondents of this study will be coming from the Junior High School and Senior High School level of Partida National High School located at Partida, San Miguel, Bulacan. Purposive sampling method, also known as selective sampling, a non-probability sampling method. This type of sampling method is better for matching sample to the aims and objectives of the research, hence improving the accuracy of the study and the reliability of the data and the results. The use of purposive sampling is one way to select

respondents who are believed to provide appropriate and useful information (Campbell et.al., 2020). Furthermore, based on Crossman (2020), a purposive sampling is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study. The total respondents of the study are forty-seven (47) teachers that are currently teaching in Partida National High School at Partida, San Miguel, Bulacan.

The data gathering procedure encompasses different steps to ensure that the collection of data will be accurate and reliable. This procedure involved three main stages: the preparation of the questionnaire, the pilot testing, and the administration of the questionnaire. The first procedure involved the reviewing of the original questionnaire to ensure that the content is relevant and clear for the current research study. This should be aligned to the demographic and specific objectives of the research. Afterwards, before the administration of the questionnaire, pilot testing for the adapted questionnaire should be done with small group of participants or ten (10) non-participating individuals who are engaged in the topic of climate change. This step will ensure that unnecessary data will be identified, and adjustments can be made based on the feedback, it will ensure that the questions will effectively measure the intended objectives. Finally, the instrument will be distributed to the target respondents, ensuring proper systematic procedures and ensured the collection of high-quality and dependable data for subsequent analysis and interpretation. The administration of the questionnaire involved several steps that needs to be taken to ensure the validity and reliability of data. The respondents should be informed about the covered topics, purpose of the study, data collection process, and the handling of information. Data security, storage, transfer, and destruction should be discussed to ensure the data will be kept confidential and secure. Finally, the questionnaire can be distributed. This questionnaire should be completed by the respondents. They should be given enough time to complete it, and the researcher must be available in time of queries and clarifications on the questionnaire.

This survey questionnaire will act as instrument for the collection of data. The research instrument that will be utilized is adapted from the study of Ratinen (2021) with the title "Students' Knowledge of Climate Change, Mitigation and Adaptation in the Context of Constructive Hope". This questionnaire aims to know the students' understanding of climate change, their knowledge about mitigation and adaptation strategies, and their whole sense of hope about climate action. The instrument uses two (2) parts; the part one tackled the "climate change knowledge", and the second part is the "climate change mitigation knowledge. These two parts of the instrument uses a 5-point Likert scale with the alternative answers: Strongly disagree-1, Disagree-2, Neither disagree nor agree- 3, Agree- 4, and Strongly Agree- 5. The first part of the instrument is composed of fourteen (14) questions that tackles the climate change knowledge of the respondents. These questions were validated with the use of Cronbach's Alpha with a result of 0.86. Second part that talks about the climate change mitigation knowledge is composed of ten (10) questions that uses the same alternative answers. The Cronbach's alpha for these items is 0.78. Analysis of data will be performed with the use of appropriate statistical tool after gathering the data. With the use of pretest, posttest, and retention test, the researcher will employ statistical analysis to examine the quantitative data. Both descriptive and

inferential statistic will be utilized to check and confirm the hypothesis of the study. To provide a clear summary of data characteristics for the variables such as sex and class type, frequency and percentage will be used to identify and interpret the profile of the respondents. While weighted mean will be used to measure the level of awareness of the teachers in understanding climate change. For the inferential statistics, to analyze the differences between the independent and dependent variables, Independent Sample T-test will be utilized. Using this tool, the differences in implementation practices based on sex and class type will be identified.

RESULTS

This study assesses the level of awareness and mitigation practices of Junior High School Teachers and Senior High School Teachers on climate change. The instrument uses two (2) parts; the part one tackled the “climate change knowledge”, and the second part is the “climate change mitigation knowledge. These two parts of the instrument uses a 5-point likert scale with the alternative answers: Strongly disagree-1, Disagree-2, Neither disagree nor agree- 3, Agree- 4, and Strongly Agree- 5.

Table 2.

Description of Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Sex	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Female	34	77.27%
Male	10	22.73%
TOTAL	44	100.00%

Table 2 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex. It can be seen from the table that majority or 77.27% of the respondents are females and the remaining 10 or 22.73% are males.

Results of the analysis imply that respondents (Junior High School and Senior High School Teachers) are dominated by females.

Table 3.

Description of Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Class Type

Class Type	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Junior High School	35	79.55 %
Senior High School	9	20.45 %
TOTAL	44	100.00%

The data in table 3 indicates that a significant majority of the respondents, 35 out of 44, or 79.55%, are Junior High School teachers. In contrast, only 9 out of 44 respondents, or 20.45%, are Senior High School teachers.

The analysis suggests that the teaching population sampled in this study is heavily skewed towards Junior High School educators. This imbalance may reflect the larger number of Junior High School positions available compared to the Senior High School.

Table 4.

Respondents' Level of Climate Change Awareness

Item Statement	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Climate change increases because...		
There is too much greenhouse gas (GHG)	4.68	Strongly Agree
Too much IR radiation stays on the Earth	4.55	Strongly Agree
We use fossil fuels such as oil and coal	4.59	Strongly Agree
Purchased products generate GHGs	4.50	Strongly Agree
Nitrogen oxides are released from fertilizers	4.34	Strongly Agree
Landfills produce methane	4.25	Strongly Agree
There is intensive forest logging	4.66	Strongly Agree
We are using nuclear power	4.05	Agree
We are using wind power	3.32	Neither Agree nor Disagree
There is too much consumption of milk and dairy products	3.41	Agree
The Earth has an ozone hole	4.39	Strongly Agree
Emitted IR radiation is absorbed by GHGs	4.16	Agree
Factories and cars increase temperature	4.59	Strongly Agree
Standard Deviation		0.89
Grand Mean	4.27	Strongly Agree

Legend:

- 4.21 - 5.00 – Strongly Agree
- 3.41 - 4.20 - Agree
- 2.61 - 3.40 – Neither Agree nor Disagree
- 1.81 - 2.60 – Disagree
- 1.00 - 1.80 – Strongly Disagree

The highest level of awareness, denoted by "strongly agree," is related to statements such as "There is too much greenhouse gas (GHG)" and "We use fossil fuels such as oil and coal," which had weighted averages of 4.68 and 4.59, respectively. Statements such as "We are using wind power" and "There is too much consumption of milk and dairy products" received lower means of 3.32 and 3.41, respectively, indicating that respondents are less aware or convinced of the impact of these issues. The standard deviation of 0.89 represents moderate response variability, while the grand mean of 4.27 indicates that, on average, respondents "strongly agree" with the listed causes' considerable impact on climate change.

The findings show that respondents are well-aware of the key causes of climate change, such as greenhouse gas emissions, fossil fuels, and industrial activities, and they are generally in agreement about their responsibilities. The lack of awareness about wind power and the impact of dairy products suggests that education should be used in this area. Overall, the findings suggest that, while the major climate change issues are well-known, increasing knowledge about lesser-known ones may improve understanding and support for comprehensive climate action.

While validating this data, Agboola and Emmanuel (2016) found that students are familiar with the concepts of climate change. Access to information and personal experiences as well as public markets and education have a profound impact on their thinking. The study also found that there was no gender difference in climate change and sustainable development awareness ($t=0.733 > 0.05$). The perception of the teachers on climate change differs significantly ($t= 0.013$).

Table 5.

Respondents' Level of Knowledge about Various Mitigation Practices

Item Statement	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
If the climate is to change as little as possible, we need to...		
use public transport more	3.66	Agree
walk and bicycle more	4.52	Strongly Agree
avoid food waste	4.52	Strongly Agree
eat local food	4.14	Agree
reducing dairy products	3.75	Agree
favour a vegetarian diet	4.02	Agree
purchase less goods	3.89	Agree
by lowering room temperature	3.82	Agree
travel inland	3.70	Agree
use trains not planes	3.57	Agree
Standard Deviation		0.97
Grand Mean	3.96	Agree

Legend:

4.21 - 5.00 – Strongly Agree

3.41 - 4.20 - Agree

2.61 - 3.40 – Neither Agree nor Disagree

1.81 - 2.60 – Disagree

1.00 - 1.80 – Strongly Disagree

The table shows the weighted means and interpretations for various climate change mitigation practices as perceived by the respondents. The highest levels of agreement,

categorized as "Strongly Agree," are associated with the statements "walk and bicycle more" and "avoid food waste," both receiving a weighted mean of 4.52.

In contrast, the "use of train, nor plane" option received a low mean of 3.57 indicating a low level of agreement. A deviation of 0.97 indicates significant difference in results, while a weighted average of 3.96 indicates an overall "Agree" sentiment and a slight tendency towards reduced dairy products. The results indicate that respondents strongly support and agree on actions such as increasing cycling and avoiding food waste as effective measures to combat climate change. While there is general agreement on several activities, such as consuming local foods and reducing dairy products, low levels of on actions such as using trains instead of flying, it suggests that some measures need to reduce consumption. The survey result strengthens and educate action in reducing climate change.

Abbass et al. (2022), discussed climate change as long-term change in global climate that represents a major problem at different levels of the world. The results showed that participants strongly agreed that activities such as encouraging cycling and preventing food waste are effective measures to combat climate change. While there is general agreement on many measures such as eating local food and reducing dairy products, disagreements on measures such as the use of train instead of flying suggest that some measures reduce emissions may not be prioritized, or even possible. The agricultural sector is particularly affected as climate change threatens the production of food and raw materials, thereby threatening global food security. It does not threatens food availability, but also accelerates ecosystem loss by altering ecosystems and pushing and may species beyond their desired temperature.

Table 6.

Test of Significant Difference on Level of Climate Change Awareness of the Respondents based on their Sex

	Mean	t-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Male	4.34	0.94	0.3453	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Female	4.25				

Legend: <0.05 = significant

The figure compares climate change awareness scores between male and female respondents. The average score for men is 4.34 and for women in 4.25, p value is 0.3453. considering that the p-value exceeds the normal significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted. This shows that there is no significant difference between male and female participants in terms of climate change perception. The results mean that gender does not play a significant role in the perception of climate change among participants. As the non-significant p-value indicates, both male and female participants show the same level of awareness. These finding suggest that climate change

perceptions are evenly distributed in this sample and that some other factors may play an important role in determining the level of campaigns.

In contrast, according to World Health Organization (WHO), (2014), women and men have different roles, behaviors, and attitudes towards addressing climate change. Surveys demonstrate that in many nations, men utilize more energy. Women typically make more domestic purchasing decisions, such as food, water, and energy, than men, especially for private transportation. Gender inequalities exist when it comes to the health and safety hazards associated with emerging technology for reducing greenhouse gases. Such data could aid in more targeted more effective efforts to implement healthy and environmentally sustainable policies.

Table 7.

Test of Significant Difference on Level of Knowledge on Mitigation Practices for Climate Change of the Respondents based on their Sex

	Mean	t-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Male	4.01	0.78	0.4355	Accept H_o	Not Significant
Female	3.94				

Legend: <0.05 = significant

The data compares the mean scores for knowledge of climate change mitigation practices between male and female respondents. The mean score for males is 4.01, while for females it is 3.94. The t-value is 0.78 with a p-value of 0.4355. Since the p-value is higher than the typical significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the level of knowledge about climate change mitigation practices between male and female respondents.

The results imply that sex does not have a significant effect on the level of knowledge regarding climate change mitigation practices among respondents. Both male and female respondents have similar levels of knowledge, as demonstrated by the non-significant p-value. This finding suggests that the understanding of mitigation practices is consistent across genders in this sample, and other factor may need to be explored to identify variations in knowledge levels.

McCright (2010), used 8 years of Gallup data on climate change awareness and concern in the US general public, this study puts theoretical claims regarding gender differences in scientific knowledge and environmental concern to the test. Contrary to expectations from scientific literacy research, women convey a higher-rated scientific understanding of climate change than men do. According to much existing sociology and science research, women underestimate their understanding of ecological change more than men do. Furthermore, women are slightly more concerned about climate change than men, and

this gender gap is not explained by differences in important values and beliefs or by the social roles that men and women play in society.

Table 8.

Test of Significant Difference on Level of Climate Change Awareness of the Respondents based on their Class Type

	Mean	t-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Junior High School	4.26	-0.31	0.7566	Accept H_o	Not Significant
Senior High School	4.30				

Legend: <0.05 = significant

This table shows the statistical comparison of climate change awareness scores among junior and senior high school level participants. The average score for high school teachers is 4.26, while senior high school teachers rate is slightly higher at 4.30. the p-value is 0.1. Considering that the 31st value exceeds the normal level of 0.05 with a p-value of 0.7566, the null hypothesis is accepted. This shows that there is no significant difference in the level of attitude towards climate change according to class level.

The results mean that type class (junior high school vs. senior high school) does not significantly change the level of climate change awareness among the participants. As the non-significant p-value indicates, both groups show the same level of awareness. These findings suggest that climate change awareness is heterogeneous phenomenon and other variables may be important in determining the differences in awareness.

Table 9.

Test of Significant Difference on Level of Knowledge on Mitigation Practices for Climate Change of the Respondents based on their Class Type

	Mean	t-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Junior High School	3.86	-4.33	0.001	Reject H_o	Significant
Senior High School	4.38				

Legend: <0.05 = significant

The data compares the average knowledge scores of respondents on climate change mitigation with high school. The average score for junior high school respondents is 3.86, while the average score for senior high school respondents is higher at 4.38. the t-value is 4.33 with a p-value of 0.001. Since the p-value is below the normal level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This shows that there are significant differences in the level of knowledge about mitigation to climate change based on class type.

The mean of the class type (junior high school vs. senior high school) has a significant effect on the level of knowledge about climate change. As indicated by the significant p-value, senior high school have higher knowledge than junior high school respondents. This study shows that junior high school respondents may be more exposed to reciprocity education and suggests the need to revise and develop information programs for high school teachers to increase understanding in educational institutions.

According to the results of the online poll (Likert scale), youngsters have low confidence in how well their education has prepared them for climate change and mitigation efforts. However, the majority (88%) believe that their activities and lifestyle choices can help reduce CC. Knowledge of the relative efficacy of GGE-reducing actions was generally poor (Wilcoxon signed rank tests and open-ended responses), with recycling overestimated and having one fewer child underestimated, implying that youth lack the necessary knowledge to maximize CC mitigation through personal choices. Our findings have implications for high school curricula, community college education, and policy in general (Pickering et al., 2020)

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the researcher had drawn the following conclusions:

1. The most numbers of the Junior High School Teachers and Senior High School Teachers are female, while the least number of teachers from JHS and SHS level and male.
2. Junior High School Teachers has the greatest number of respondents compared to the number of Senior High School Teachers.
3. Majority of the respondents shows a high level of awareness about the major contributors to climate change such as the greenhouse gases, fossil fuels, and industrial activities. Though there are low levels of awareness on the benefits and impact of wind power and dairy consumption.
4. The study found that walking and bicycling, and avoiding food wastes are the most effective mitigation practices that are most used by the respondents. General level of usage on eating local food and reducing dairy products as mitigation practices. While there is a low level of prioritization on using trains instead of planes.
5. There were no significant correlations between the level of climate change awareness among the male and female respondents which significantly means that both sex exhibit similar levels of awareness on climate change.
6. The study shows that there were no significant difference on the level of knowledge on climate change and their mitigation practices. Both sex shows that there is a similar level of knowledge on climate change, and mitigation practices understanding is consistent on both male and female.
7. The class type of the respondents has no significant influence on the level of climate change awareness. It shows that there is a uniform awareness of climate change across different class types.
8. There is a significant correlation between the level of knowledge regarding climate change and the respondent's mitigation practices. Senior High School teachers'

respondents have a higher level of knowledge compared to Junior High School teachers.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the researcher had drawn the following recommendations:

1. Teachers from Junior and Senior High School should enhance their professional development. Workshops and seminar should be organized to develop and enhance teaching practices, resources, and strategies.
 2. Integrate comprehensive climate change education in the current curriculum. This should include information about benefits of renewable energy, such as wind power at environmental impacts of dietary choices.
 3. Awareness campaign should be organized to share knowledge and understand the broader impacts of climate change.
 4. Community involvement should be incorporated to provide real-world context and support to the teachers, students, and community. This might help the wider community to address climate change.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The assent forms should be distributed to treat the data with high confidentiality and utmost consideration of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 and DepEd Regional Memorandum No. 228, s. 2020 entitled "*Policy Guidelines on the Adherence to Ethical Research Principles and Responsibilities in Studies Involving Teaching, Teaching Related, Non-Teaching Personnel and Learners*".

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